

Civil War in Syria and Libya after Arab Spring

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ABSTRACT

The wave of Arab Spring which started from Tunisia at the ending of 2010, by a young graduate and vegetable vender, and after setting himself on the fire due to harassment and insult by a police women, after suicide by the young vegetable vender there's people began the protest against the government and their officials, then soon after this protest transformed as a heavy conflict between Tunisian people and government. And further this conflict followed by Egypt. Soon after this wave sparked in the whole Arab countries as major or minor like Libya, Syria, Yemen Lebanon, Morocco, Jordon and etc. This Uprising wave developed in some countries as the civil war like Libya, Yemen and Syria. The Civil war in Libya and Syria which started after suppression to the demonstrators by the governments and their security forces in both countries. Similarly the foreign interventions are also caused to develop and transfer the Arab Uprising towards the civil war in the above countries. This civil war is caused a lot of losses and human crisis in both countries as well as it caused to flee from their homes in other places in same country or neighbour countries. This civil war resulted as hundreds of thousand's death from both sides, the supporters of the governments and their rivals, and similarly resulted as millions of people's migration. The main objective of this paper is to analyse the situation of both countries as well as to know the causes of the war and its result in both countries. The methodology is adopted in the present paper is qualitative.

KEYWORDS: Arab Spring, Civil War, Causes, Results, Libya, and Syria

INTRODUCTION

The Arab Uprising which started from an African country "Tunisia" by the ending of 2010 by a young vegetable vender Mohamed Bouazizi and after setting himself on the fire due to harassment and insult by a police woman, after suicide by the young vegetable vender, there's people began the protest in supporting of vender and against the government and their officials, then soon after this protest transformed as a heavy conflict between Tunisian people and government and further this conflict followed by Egypt and many Arab countries as Libya, Syria Yemen, Jordon, Morocco and etc.[1] The main objective of this uprising is to regime change and it became a very famous slogan of this uprising in the whole Arab world as "الشباب يريد إسقاط النظام" the people want to overthrow the regime.[2] This protest was both kind violence and non-violence. In some countries this protest developed as civil war like Libya, Syria and Yemen. In Libya this protest started in the mid of February 2011 at Benghazi after arrest a young human rights lawyer named was Fathi Terbil. Its supporters are mobilized peacefully and demanded to release him, but security forces did not release him and they response as to firing upon them. After this action of the Security forces this protest spread in the whole country, and after the foreign intervention this conflict developed as civil war. Similarly in Syria this protest occurred after arrest 15 teenagers when they wrote the slogan "الشباب يريد إسقاط النظام" "the people want overthrow the regime" on the walls and rocks. After arresting the children, their parents, other relatives and social activists are gathered to release the children and they started protest to release the arrested children, then the security forces

cracked down and killed more than 100 people among the protesters. After this brutal action of the forces on the protesters, this kind of protest sparked in many places of the country and gradually took a face of mass level demonstration against the government and its security forces that killed the innocent people. After foreign intervention as United State of America, United Kingdom, Russia, Iran, Saudi Arabia, Qatar and Turkey this conflict developed as a civil war. Due to this war both countries are facing so many problems in their life. This civil war resulted as a lot of losses like death, injuries, decease, hungry, unemployment, displaces, migration and etc.

ARAB SPRING:

The Arab Spring is a kind of protest and demonstration against the governments and their rulers. This protest and demonstration which is known as "Arab Spring" started from Tunisia by the ending of 2010, when a young graduate Tunisian vegetable and fruit seller "Mohamed Bouazizi" set himself on the fire due to insulting and distracting him by the government's people particularly by a police woman. After that Tunisian people started the protests and demonstrations on the streets of Tunisia against the government. In a very short time this protest sparked in the whole country. After Tunisia this wave of Uprising spread in Egypt and in the whole Arab world like Libya, Syria, Yemen, Lebanon, Morocco and Jordon in a very short time.[3] This protest has many objectives and goals behind it. The common objective of the whole Arab world was "إسقاط النظام" "regime change" and it was the most famous slogan of the

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whole Arab world for this protest and demonstration as “الشباب يريد إسقاط النظام” “the Arab people want to overthrow the regime”.

Therefore the regime change is seen in many Arab countries as major changes or minor changes, like Tunisia, Egypt, Libya and Yemen.[4] Meanwhile in some countries this change was fugacious like Egypt and Libya, and in other some countries this was durable like Tunisia. After this protest in some countries the fair and free elections are held and democratic governments are established like Tunisia and Egypt. But this democratic government is governed for a very short period in Egypt, and it is continue in Tunisia. In other some countries this protest transferred as civil war like Syria, Yemen and Libya, and this civil war is going on in Syria and Libya very badly, and this war is resulted as millions death and millions migration and displaces within the country or other countries.

CIVIL WAR:

A Civil War is a kind of war which is fought between groups within the same state or country. According to Nicholas Sambanis a civil war is as “any armed conflict that involves a military action internal to the metropolis, the active participation of the national government and active resistance by both sides”. [5] James Fearon defined a civil war as “a violent conflict within a country fought by organized groups that aim to take power at the centre or region or to change government policies”. [6] The Civil wars and this kind of large-scale violence bring death, injury, disease, misery, unemployment, starvation, displacement and migration.

CIVIL WAR IN SYRIA:

The first time protest “Arab Spring” started in Syria on 18 March, 2011, at dusty agricultural town of Dar’a near the border with Jordan. More than fifteen schoolchildren are arrested and they are brutally tortured for writing the slogan “الشباب يريد إسقاط النظام” “the people want to overthrow the regime” on the walls and rocks, it was a very famous slogan in this Uprising in all the Arab countries where the Arab Spring sparked. After arresting the children their guardians and other adults of that region began the peacefully protest to release their children, thousands of people rapidly mobilized and joined them. Then the Syrian forces cracked down on the demonstrations and killed more than 100 people. After killing the innocent people the protests started in other cities of the country and gradually this protest spread in the whole country and it shaped a mass level protest. Then it had become very difficult for the Syrian government and its security forces to stop the protesters and demonstrations, the demonstrators was demanding to overthrow the regime of President Bashar Assad who got this post “president ship” in hereditary in 2000, after his father’s death.[7]

The brutal repression of peaceful protesters and demonstrators pushed the country towards a civil war.[8] These protests and demonstrations refer a very high level conflict between President Bashar al- Assad, its security forces and anti-government rebel forces. After near about three years of this conflict, it resulted as more than 125,000 people, out of a Syrian population of approximately 22 million, have died in the fighting, and similarly one third of the population has fled the country or has been displaced

internally.[9] This civil war ruined the economic condition of Syria. In terms of domestic economy this civil war has destroyed infrastructure, prevented the children from going to school, closed factories, and deterred overall investments and trade. After this war the Syrian people are also facing a high level unemployment at 57 percent, while in 2013 Syria’s GDP dropped a surprisingly 20.6 percent. According to the European Council on Foreign Relations the Syrian HDI has fallen back to where it was 38 years ago, it means that today the average Syrian has the same life expectancy, education and employment prospects as in 1977.[10] It is estimated by United Nation if the civil war was to end the damage will be similar as some nations of Second World War and it will take 40-50 years to fully recover.

CIVIL WAR IN LIBYA:

The wave of Arab Uprising which started in Libya after inspired with revolt in other Arab countries, especially two North African neighbour countries as Tunisia and Egypt. Whereas many Libyan people were against Clonal-Muammar Gaddafi and his government due to human rights violation, social program mismanagement, and political corruption. But the protest “Arab spring” began in 15 February 2011 at Benghazi after arrest the young human rights lawyer activist Fathi Terbil. After arresting Fathi Terbil its supporters gathered peacefully outside the local police station to release him, but the security forces did not release him and they fired upon the protesters. After that this protest spread in the whole Libyan cities and towns, the demonstrators became the rebels. During protests at many places the clashes erupted between demonstrators and security forces and it resulted as thousands of casualties and deaths from both sides. According to reports the government’s forces were using tanks and warplanes against demonstrators and executing those officers who refused to deploy the instruments of the state against its people.

A coalition body (National Transitional Council) of anti-Gaddafi forces is formed in Libya on February 27 to consolidate resistance efforts nation-wide. This coalition body solidified its agenda and mobilized, after that Gaddafi cracked down in retaliation. After Gaddafi’s this action the peaceful protests transformed into a bloody civil war, which was only officially ended with Gaddafi’s death on October 20, 2011, and the NTC declared the victory. This conflict developed into an internationally recognized as civil war.[11] After Gaddafi’s killing it did not bring any relief to the country, but it has fallen into uncontrolled violence, a civil war that can be called multi-factional. In August 2012 the National Transitional Council hand over the power to General National Congress (GNC) and Ali Zeidan is elected as the Prime Minister by General National Congress of Tripoli on October 14, 2012, and Ali Zeidan is stepped down on March 11, 2014, and replaced by Abdullah Al-Thani. On June, 2014 a legislative body the Council of Dispute organized new elections in order to substitute the GNC. The result is declared in the favour of more secular and moderate wing at the expense of Islamists who did not accept it, declaring a sort of continuing mandate foe GNC, and occupying the capital Tripoli. The Libyan leadership is split in two governments one based on a secular matrix and its headquarter is in Tobruk and supported by the House of Representatives (HoR) and recognized internationally, abetted by General Khalifa Haftrar and by the Zintan brigades the militias coming from the ethnic minorities of

Tebu and Fezzan. The Other hand the Islamic has his headquarter in Tripoli and supported by New General National Congress and by the more Islamist militias coming from Misrata, amazigh and Tuareg, as its armed wing.[12] In fact the militias are against GNC and conflict started between them for taking power, and the Libyan government and Parliament divided between them and second civil war began in Libya between rivals of Gaddafi.

CAUSES:

In fact, after the Arab Spring in Libya two civil wars are found one of them which started in February as the Arab uprising as well as it had started from Tunisia and Egypt respectively and it developed as civil war in Libya between security forces and rebel forces in response of arresting the human rights' lawyer and activist Fathi Terbil and killing of their supporters by the security forces, and this civil war ended after Muammar Gaddafi's killing in October 20, 2011, and second civil war which started after the killing of Gaddafi between secularism and Islamism. There are five main factors which involved to developing the conflict into the civil war in Libya. As they are follows,

1. The nature and actions of previous regime, including rise to power, makeup of the regime, public access to information and political dissent, and amenability to reform.
2. The Division of the State in to government and rebel-controlled territories with loosely or clearly defined battlegrounds, and the ability of the players to gain local support and resource access in these home bases.
3. Militarization the government and rebel forces, including the loss of monopoly of force by the government and the ability and willingness of the rebel forces to arm and train its members through either internal or external means into cohesive and united troops.
4. International interference, in the form of state, international organization, and NGO approval, aid, and/or intervention, and the nature of international media coverage influencing policymaking.
5. Regional player, including the approval of bordering nations, regional organizations, and the flow of goods and services through borders.[13]

In Syria the civil war started in the face of Arab uprising in March 2011. The most of Syrian people especially Sunni people was against Assad's regime, and this post (president) was inherited to Assad in 2000 after his father's death, and the Syrian people want to overthrow Assad's regime, and they want to establish a new democratic government. Hundreds of Syrians have organized a rare protest in the capital, Damascus, calling for democratic reforms and the release of all political prisoners.[14] But after repressing the anti-government protests by the security forces, the protesters became angry and they spread this wave in the whole country and demonstrated as mass level.[15] The Assad's security forces cracked down on the demonstrators and killed hundreds of protesters and along with a couple of thousands protesters are injured. After taking this action by the Syrian government these protesters became the rebels of the government. After intervention the external governments and external forces this conflict developed as civil war and it refers to political, military and operational support to parties in the ongoing conflict in Syria. Which resulted as more than 250,000 death and more than 11

million others have been forced to leave their homes in four and a half years of armed conflict in Syria.[16]

Foreign interventions in Syrian conflict are widely described as a series of overlapping proxy wars between regional and world powers, Primarily between Russia and United States, as well as Iran and Saudi Arabia.[17] The Syrian Assad's government is politically and military supported by internal governments as Iran and Russia, as well as supported by internal party (Lebanese Hezbollah).[18] The Syrian opposition is politically and military supported by foreign governments as U.S, France, U.K, and it supported by major Sunni states as Saudi Arabia, Qatar and Turkey. While the Syrian opposition politically represented by Syrian National Coalition. In Syria Sunni and Shia conflict is also a main factor to develop this conflict towards the civil war as well as the foreign intervention. The Shia group people support to Assad's government as well as Shia country (Iran) fully support to Assad's regime while Sunni people are against the Assad's government.

CONCLUSION:

After eruption the Arab Uprising in the Arab world, which started from Tunisia at the ending of 2010 and shortly this uprising spread in the most of the Arab countries like Egypt, Libya, Syria and Yemen etc. In some Arab countries this movement developed as the civil war like Libya and Syria. This civil war resulted as a lot of losses, human crisis, unemployment and other social problems in both countries. After analysing the above paragraphs it is clear that this uprising "Arab Spring" is totally failure in most of the Arab world and it was success in some countries, and it caused to create so many problems in the Arab world and it also caused to human crisis as well as financial crisis in these region. Through the above lines it is realised too that after foreign interventions, this conflict developed as the civil war which experienced a very deleterious to the Arab people. The Sunni and Shia groups conflict also a main factor to create high level civil war and for a long term in Syria as well as foreign intervention. Due to this conflict, fear of killing and dangerous situations in both countries, millions of people fled and displaced from their homes to take shelter in other places in same country or other countries too. The main purpose of this conflict was to "regime change" reform and to create democratic governments but the Arab people could not achieve their objectives and could not success in their actions but actually it was failure in both countries. In Syria the brutal Assad's government could not change in previous regime and could not reform in previous government system, as well as in Libya the ruler is changed but the main objective and purpose is not found "democratic government". Now the people of Libya also are facing so many problems in the country after this uprising and overthrow the old government.

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